

1 **Homeoboxes induced during resistance to chemotherapy *in vitro* in TNBC.**

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7 We discovered homeoboxes induced during resistance to chemotherapy in triple negative breast cancer
8 using *in vitro* cellular systems and RNA-sequencing. *Tbx18* was the molecule most significantly induced
9 transcriptome wide. *IRX2* was also produced in large quantities. *Sox7*, *Tcl6*, and pluripotency factors
including those of the *KLF* and *POU5F* family were activated. A pattern of de-differentiation from the
TNBC homeobox commitment program emerged suggesting intelligent subtype switching to engage
alternative resources during chemotherapeutic challenge, and included *TCF19* silencing. Multiple Fox
family homeobox factors were mobilized during resistance to chemotherapy.

10 Citations

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